

Materials for teaching mathematics to upper secondary migrant or minority students

Andreas Ulovec, University of Vienna, andreas.ulovec@univie.ac.at

Jarmila Novotná, Charles University and Université Bordeaux

The multicultural nature of society influences education in many countries. Support for teachers is available, but mostly for languages and social sciences. Therefore, many mathematics teachers feel a pressing need for materials supporting them in teaching in multicultural classrooms. A lot of mathematics teaching materials exist for different settings, though most of those do not take migrant students or multicultural settings into consideration. Very few have been created specifically for migrants, but those are mostly for younger students in elementary grades. Following the guidelines developed in a Czech-Austrian collaboration project, we therefore want to propose mathematics teaching units for upper secondary migrant students.

Theoretical background

A lot of mathematics teachers work in socially and ethically heterogeneous classrooms. Many of them feel not sufficiently prepared to deal with a classroom context of pupils having a migrant or minority background, coming from countries or parts of the society with different cultures and different languages (Moraová, Novotná, & Favilli, 2018). Mathematics teachers in all grades feel the necessity of training and materials which reflect the needs of their students in terms of linguistic and cultural differences. There is a fairly large body of literature dealing with language issues in teaching mathematics to migrant students (e.g., Prediger et al., 2018; Gutiérrez, 2002), or with various teaching strategies (e.g., Moschkovich, 2010; Bose, 2021). There is – thankfully – also a growing body of literature advising researchers, curriculum authors, textbook developers etc. about taking an equity approach that does not stop at language, but takes cultural, socio-political and gender issues into consideration as well (e.g., Gutiérrez, 2013; Leder, 2019; Moschkovich 2013). A good overview of that literature has been provided by Civil (2020) and Barwell et al. (2016), who also clarify the terms and outline various research directions. Despite that large body of literature, not a lot of actual concrete teaching materials exist in this area, and what is there is mainly for younger students in elementary and lower secondary grades. So it is particularly important for upper secondary mathematics teachers to be able to design suitable teaching units (or modify existing units) that allow students to see reality from different perspectives, and also to develop greater self-knowledge and awareness of cultural differences and how they can

Please cite as: Ulovec, A., & Novotná, J. (2021). Materials for teaching mathematics to upper secondary migrant or minority students. In D. Kolloosche (Ed.), *Exploring new ways to connect: Proceedings of the Eleventh International Mathematics Education and Society Conference* (Vol. 3, pp. 1033–1042). Tredition. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5457244>

advance one's own learning. Such units should be carefully designed, following the principles of culturally responsive teaching and equity pedagogy. Novotná, Ulovec and Moraová (2020) developed criteria that can be applied to such teaching units for them to be appropriate to be used in culturally heterogeneous classrooms. These criteria ask for teaching units to (inter alia)

- foster tolerance and help to overcome linguistic and cultural differences,
- be of interest for both minority and majority pupils,
- value diversity,
- refer to environments familiar to all pupils,
- make use of different cultural backgrounds as “funds of knowledge”,
- use a variety of contexts, names and places from multiple cultures to allow children to better be able to relate to them,
- avoid cultural stereotypes and prejudice,
- use culturally responsive teaching and equity pedagogy.

Even though mathematics is often seen as abstract matter, particularly to upper secondary students, it could become somewhat closer to them and their reality by using experiences from their own lives. The use of everyday objects like ornaments or electric appliances gives the subject an affective aspect and an emotional dimension not to be neglected, and can be a source of increased creativity.

The concept of Substantial learning environment (SLE) was introduced by Wittmann (1995). It is an educational environment meeting several criteria: It has a simple starting point; it represents objectives, contents, and principles of teaching mathematics at a certain level; it is a rich source of mathematical activities; it is flexible and can be adapted to the special conditions of a classroom; it integrates mathematical, psychological and pedagogical aspects of teaching mathematics.

SLE forms a rich field for empirical research. The presented paper focuses on one aspect of the educational domain. It shows that SLE supports teaching in culturally and socially heterogeneous classes and students' and teachers' creativity. SLE also motivates students to understand the importance of mathematics for all domains of life regardless their heterogeneity. The piloting of the presented teaching units (amongst a number of other ones) justifies that it has the potential of meeting the needs of students attending schools at present with their cultural and linguistic diversity. The use of objects from everyday life gives mathematics an important affective dimension.

Substantial learning environments also support creativity in mathematics lessons – both on the teachers' and the students' part – and can be used to create teaching units for multicultural classrooms. Being given the cultural background, teachers are motivated to use their creative potential to look for the mathematics that can be discovered and taught in the particular environment.

Methodology

Following the above-mentioned criteria, we propose materials for three teaching units in mathematics for culturally heterogeneous classrooms in upper secondary school. We shall describe the first unit in depth, and give a short synopsis of the other units.

For the development process of the list of criteria described above, we refer to Ulovec, Novotná and Moraová (2021) and Novotná, Moraová and Ulovec (2021). The development process of the original teaching units on which our proposed units below are based is described in depth by Favilli (2015). There, a three-step development was followed: Each teaching unit was proposed and piloted by one group of authors (a team of linguists and mathematics educators), tested unchanged by a group of mathematics teachers and teacher educators, then modified, and the modified version was piloted again by yet another group of mathematics teachers and teacher educators. Since we based our proposal on three units that went through such a rigorous development process, we did not feel the need to go through that whole process with our units again. We did take the three original units, modified them according to the above-mentioned criteria, and then piloted them in a regular school setting, as described in detail at the unit below.

Teaching unit example 1: Parabolas to cook with

Introduction

This unit is based on the idea that ecology and the environment are topics of interest for students of many cultural backgrounds. Also, it can be a good activity to start a discussion about why not everywhere in the world people can prepare food in the way and with the means that we are used to in so-called industrialized countries. The concept of this unit was developed by Pointner (2016).

The unit is intended to be used for secondary school grade 7 (age of students: 17 years). It can either be used as a 1 lesson activity (to introduce parabolas and some of their properties), or as a 2-3 lesson activity if the proofs are also included.

Description of the teaching unit

The unit can start with a discussion activity to think about cooking with solar energy. Either the students come up with a picture of a “solar cooker” (e.g. from the Internet), or the teacher introduces the picture from the teaching materials. The students can then discuss about why this “solar cooker” actually works.

The remaining lesson is mainly a teacher-centred activity where certain properties of a parabola are introduced. Depending on the time, interest of students, and mathematical level of the class, the proofs can either be worked on by the students, introduced by the teacher, being used as study material or exam preparation, or skipped entirely.

The lesson can end with a brainstorming activity about other applications of parabolas or paraboloids (satellite TV, dishes for communication and radar, etc.).

Teaching materials for this unit

Introduction

When you think about cooking with solar energy, you probably imagine something like this:

Figure 1: Oven powered by solar energy (drawn by ourselves using MS Paint)

Solar cells (photovoltaic cells) are used to convert sunlight into electricity, which can then be used to power electric devices such as ovens. In many places of the world, however, this is not a practical or affordable solution.

A much simpler way of cooking with solar energy looks like this:

Figure 2: Solar cooker (picture by Solar Power Nepal e.V.; this society is dissolved by now)

But how and why does this work? Let's look at it from a mathematical point of view.

This device, in its basic form, is a paraboloid. A paraboloid, in turn, is a surface that can be thought of as a generalized version of a parabola. We will come back to this a little later. Let's first have a look at the basic form of a parabola.

What is a parabola?

Definition: A parabola is the set of all points in a plane that have the same distance from both a given point F and a given line l . The point F is called the *focal point*, the line l is called the *directrix*.

$$par = \{X \in \mathbb{R}^2 \mid \overline{XF} = \overline{Xl}\}$$

This definition does at first glance not give us a lot of insight into what a parabola actually looks like. It does, however, give us a way to construct a parabola: We start with a line l and a point F (which is not on the line). We call the distance $\overline{Fl} = p$. p is also called the *parameter of the parabola*. Then we pick an arbitrary number $d > \frac{p}{2}$ and draw a parallel line with a distance d from l . We then set the compass to distance d , put the needle point into F , draw a circle, and intersect it with the line that we just drew:

Figure 3: Parabola construction, step 1

We have now constructed two points that have the same distance from F and l , i.e. by its definition, two points of the parabola.

If we pick other arbitrary values for d with $d > \frac{p}{2}$, we can get more points of the parabola. The finished construction looks like this:

Figure 4: Parabola construction, step 2

The point V which is closest to the line l (and exactly half way between F and l) is called the vertex.

Properties of a parabola

We have not started cooking yet! Let us therefore see what happens if a ray (e.g. of sunlight) is coming in from the open side of the parabola, parallel to the x -Axis, and is reflected at the inside of the parabola (which means it is reflected at the tangent to the parabola at the point where the ray hits the parabola).

Figure 5: Reflection of a ray of light at a parabola

The reflected ray passes directly through the focal point F . This is true for any ray coming in parallel to the x -Axis. If many parallel rays come in, the situation looks like this:

Figure 6: Reflection of numerous rays of light at a parabola

From a parabola to a paraboloid

Now of course we cannot cook with a parabola, which is a curve. But we can get a surface by rotating a parabola around an axis of rotation, thereby forming a so-called surface of revolution. If we take a standard parabola and rotate it around the x -Axis, we get a paraboloid, which also has the property that all rays coming in parallel to the axis of rotation are reflected into the focal point. Now we can take any reflective material (sheet metal, tinfoil, ...) and form this surface with it, and we get a mirror that reflects all the incoming sunlight (and thermal radiation) into one point. If we place a pot or other cookware in the position of the focal point, the content gets heated. This is exactly how a solar cooker works. Depending on the actual construction (and of course if the sun is shining), a solar cooker can reach temperatures of 150 °C to 180 °C.

Piloting of the teaching unit

Given the current situation, the unit had to be piloted in a distance learning setting. This was done in a culturally heterogeneous 7th grade class (11 out of 24 students had a first language that was not the language of instruction) in Vienna by a teacher with 5 years teaching experience. Students were asked to find videos about solar cookers in the internet, and a surprising variety of videos were found, which provided ample material for discussions. The links to all videos were put on the Moodle page for the class. Some of the videos were shown during the teaching unit. The unit was then conducted as planned and described above (in distance learning mode using Moodle). After the teaching unit, online interviews were conducted with the teacher and with 3 students (two of which had a migrant background). The teacher reported that students were very motivated during this unit, and that lively discussions (in the chat) took place. Students particularly debated about why electricity is not sufficiently provided to certain parts of the world, about fair distribution of resources, and about how this method of cooking is done for fun by “western” nationals e.g. in Canada or the USA, but as a survival strategy in other parts of the world (as demonstrated by some of the videos). The teacher also reported that students had difficulties with going from the parabola in two dimensions to the paraboloid in three dimensions, and that she would recommend covering this step more in detail than it currently is. Student A (female, with Turkish roots) found the topic very interesting, and particularly liked the fact that students were asked to look for videos (“not something we usually do in mathematics”, she commented). She also commented that the graphic representations that were given during the unit (in GeoGebra) helped her a lot to understand the different steps. Student B (female, no migrant background) enjoyed the discussions in the chat but regretted that the discussion could not be done in a presence setting (“in normal teaching”, she said). She also reported having difficulties with “going from the plane to the space just like that”, but enjoyed that “we could see that math can be used, like, for real”. Student C (male, with Afghani roots) was very engaged during the chat discussion, and particularly wondered why the “fun cooking” videos from USA always showed male cooks while the “real life daily cooking” videos from Africa or Central America showed female cooks only. He suggested having a discussion

about gender roles in a future lesson. He commented on enjoying the brainstorming activity at the end of the lesson where he provided some of the inputs about other real-life applications of paraboloids.

In general, the piloting showed that the motivational effect of the material was fairly high both for migrant and non-migrant students, the hoped-for equity discussions actually exceeded our expectations, but that the step from two to three dimensions has to be improved and be gone through in more detail.

Teaching unit example 2: Ornaments

The simple starting point in this case is a number of ornaments whose origin is in different cultures, with the intention of allowing minority pupils to be heard, to present ornaments typical for their culture or home, to break the wall between home and school, between mathematics naturally used at home and mathematics used at school (Meaney & Lange, 2012).

Ornaments undoubtedly meet the criteria of a substantial learning environment. They offer a rich source of mathematics (they can be used when teaching tens of different topics and areas) and at the same time allow the introduction of culturally heterogeneous contexts, show that very different cultures have very different but equally elaborate and intriguing ornaments, and provide space for creativity – drawing ornaments, tiling, making tessellations, bringing photographs and images from home and using them as a background to mathematics and art activity. For details, see Moraová, Novotná and Favilli (2018).

Teaching unit example 3: Magic squares

The aim of this unit is to have the students work at the same time on decimal numeration and on the use of the language of instruction, in writing and speaking in mathematics, both in terms of vocabulary and explaining one's reasoning. It is also to allow verbal exchanges about written and oral numeration used yesterday and today in various countries and to highlight the input of other civilizations to the construction of mathematics in Europe. This unit is based on this ancient magic square discovered in 1956.

The proposal concerns arithmetical concepts. The work context refers to the decrypting of an old magic square discovered in China. The activity aims at revisiting already known concepts in order to improve students' knowledge and to explicitly express certain fundamental properties, as well as at developing symbol sense. In other words, it promotes a meta-cognitive analysis of concepts in Arithmetic to clarify the relation "natural number – symbolic representation", and therefore the relation "digit – position – value" and finally the "order of magnitude" concept. Hence it faces the cognitive obstacle corresponding to the epistemological obstacle when passing from number concept to numeral concept. In addition, the proposal gives rise to significant opportunities for introducing both the demonstration activity and the algebraic thought, and for thinking on geometrical questions. The learning context is suitable to promote the development of language skills in understanding and writing a text and in explaining plans, strategies and solutions. For details, see Favilli (2015).

Summary and outlook

The piloting described in this paper and other results already published (Novotná, Ulovec, & Moraová, 2020) showed that these and other teaching units based on the inclusive criteria list above are motivating to both migrant and non-migrant students, and that they also elicited debates in the classroom about equity that went beyond the mathematical content of the lessons.

There have been several projects focusing on the effects of linguistic and cultural heterogeneity in classrooms from different perspectives. But the question of suitable materials for multicultural classrooms in the school practice, their recommended form, availability etc., still remains. To get to more useful answers, following the recommendations of Alrø, Skovsmose and Valero (2003), and following the structure of Barwell et al. (2016), we plan to analyse real teaching episodes that are carefully planned together with the involved teachers, observe them in multicultural classrooms, and include interviews with school leaders, teachers and students on a broader scale. Also, we will continue to explore possible ICT support (which we started doing in Ulovec and Novotná 2021).

Acknowledgements

We dedicate this work to our friend and colleague Angela Brychta, who recently lost her life in a tragic mountaineering accident.

References

- Alrø, H., Skovsmose O., & Valero, P. (2003). Communication, conflict and mathematics education in the multicultural classroom. In M. A. Mariotti (Ed.), *Proceedings of the Third Conference of the European Society for Research in Mathematics Education*. Pisa: University Press.
- Barwell, R., & Kaiser, G. (2005). Mathematics education in culturally diverse classrooms. *ZDM Mathematics Education*, 37(2), 61–63.
- Barwell, R., Chapsam, L., Nkambule, T., & Phakeng, M. S. (2016). Tensions in teaching mathematics in contexts of language diversity. In R. Barwell et al. (Eds.), *Mathematics education and language diversity* (pp. 175–192). Springer.
- Bose, A. (2021): Fostering meaning in a trilingual mathematics classroom by connecting everyday and school mathematical ways of talking: A design approach. *ZDM Mathematics Education*, 53, 405–417.
- César, M., & Favilli, F. (2005). Diversity seen through teachers' eyes: Discourses about multicultural classes. In M. Bosch (Ed.), *Proceedings of the Fourth Congress of the European Society for Research in Mathematics Education* (pp. 1153–1164). Sant Feliu de Guíxols: FUNDEMI IQS.
- Civil, M. (2020). Immigrant students in mathematics education. In S. Lerman (Ed.) *Encyclopedia of mathematics education* (pp. 359–365). Springer.
- Favilli, F. (Ed.) (2015). *Multiculturalism, migration, mathematics education and language. Teachers' needs and teaching materials*. M3EaL project. Tipografia Editrice Pisana.
- Gutiérrez, R. (2002). Beyond essentialism: The complexity of language in teaching mathematics to Latina/o students. *American Educational Research Journal*, 39(4), 1047–1088.
- Gutiérrez, R. (2013). The sociopolitical turn in mathematics education. *Journal for Research in Mathematics Education*, 44, 37–68.

- Leder, G. (2019). Gender and mathematics education: An overview. In G. Kaiser & N. Presmeg (Eds.), *Compendium for early career researchers in mathematics education* (pp. 289-308). Springer.
- Meaney, T., & Lange, T. (2012). Learners in transition between contexts. In M. K. Clements et al. (Eds.) *Third international handbook of mathematics education* (pp. 169-201). Springer.
- Moraová, H., Novotná, J., & Favilli, F. (2018). Ornaments and tessellations: Encouraging creativity in the mathematics classroom. In F. M. Singer (Ed.), *Mathematical creativity and mathematical giftedness: Enhancing creative capacities in mathematically promising students* (pp. 253–284). Springer.
- Moschkovich, J. (Ed.) (2010). *Language and mathematics education: Multiple perspectives and directions for research*. Information Age.
- Moschkovich, J. (2013). Principles and guidelines for equitable mathematics teaching practices and materials for English language learners. *Journal of Urban Mathematics Education*, 6(1), 45–57.
- Novotná, J., Moraová, H. & Ulovec, A. (2021, August). Three pillars for creation of teaching units for heterogeneous classes – are they suitable for elementary mathematics lessons? Paper presented at the *International Symposium Elementary Mathematics Teaching*, Prague.
- Novotná, J., Ulovec, A. & Moraová, H. (2020). Teaching mathematics to migrant or minority students: Concept for creating materials. In D. Szarková, D. Richtáriková & M. Prášilová (Eds.) *Proceedings of the 19th Conference on Applied Mathematics* (pp. 834-841). Red Hook, NY: Curran Associates.
- Pointner, S. (2016). *Kulinarische Mathematik* [Diploma thesis, University of Vienna].
- Prediger, S., Wilhelm, N., Büchter, A., Gürsoy, E., & Benholz, C. (2018). Language proficiency and mathematics achievement. *Journal für Mathematik-Didaktik*, 39(1), 1–26.
- Ulovec, A. & Novotná, J. (2021, October). From concept to teaching unit: Creating ICT-supported mathematics teaching units based on multicultural-classroom-aware concepts. Paper presented at the *20th European Conference on e-Learning*, Berlin.
- Ulovec, A., Novotná, J. & Moraová, H. (2021, July). Developing concepts for mathematics teaching units with a focus on migrant and minority students. Paper presented at the *14th International Congress on Mathematical Education*, Shanghai.
- Wittmann, E. Ch. (1995). Mathematics education as a “Design Science”. *Educational Studies in Mathematics*, 29, 355–374.